

Lengua

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Secondary source

Entered by Emily Pitek, Human Relations Area Files

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** Secondary Source entry, prepared from a literature review by a Ph.D. RA*

Entry tags: South American Religions, Religious Group

The Lengua are native to the Paraguayan Chaco of South America. In 1889 the Church of England South American Missionary Society began to work in the Lengua's native territory as missionary Barbroke Grubb began a 20 year residence among the Lengua living by the Chaco bank of the Paraguay River. Although Grubb was not an anthropologist, his detailed field notes from this time have become the principal ethnographic authority on the Lengua. This entry focuses on the Lengua band in contact with the mission around the time of 1889. At this time, the Lengua were living in autonomous bands and villages with little social distinctions; chiefs only held rule when needed for the common good (such as in times of war). Magical-practitioners were present, with their main task to protect the village from supernatural evils. These practitioners could also affect the weather and foretell future events. The Lengua supernatural beings included a vague and otiose creator deity (symbolized by a beetle), kilyikhama (malignant spirits), aphanagak (departed souls of men, who would stay around for about a month after death, then traveling to the afterlife), and departed souls of lower creations. Various feasts and religious celebrations were held throughout the year. Religion does not exist within a distinct sphere but rather permeates all aspects of life; this entry considers the religious group to be coterminous with Lengua society.

Date Range: 1869 CE - 1895 CE

Region: Paraguayan Chaco

Region tags: South America, Paraguay

Paraguayan Chaco region circa 1889, specifically, the Lengua band in contact with the Paraguayan Chaco Mission.

Status of Participants:

✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Tuden, A. & Marshall, C. (Oct., 1972). Political organization: Cross-cultural codes 4. *Ethnology*, 11(4), 436-464.
- Source 2: Grubb, W.B. (1913). *An unknown people in an unknown land*. London.
- Source 3: Hawtrey, S.H.C. (1901). The Lengua Indians of the Paraguayan Chaco. *Journal of the Royal Anthropological Institute*. 31:280-299.
- Source 1: Murdock, G.P. & Wilson, S.F. (Jul., 1972). Settlement patterns and community organization: Cross-Cultural Codes 3. *Ethnology*, 11(3), 254-295.
- Source 2: Divale, W. 2004. Codebook of Variables for the Standard Cross-Cultural Sample. *World Cultures*:

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: "In the year 1889 the Church of England South American Missionary Society began a work in the Paraguayan Chaco, and in the following pages the pioneer missionary and explorer [Grubb] recounts his experiences and adventures, and gives the results of studies and researches covering a period of twenty years, during which he lives in the heart of the Indian fastness among the tribe of the Lenguas" (Grubb, 1913:vii).

Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– No

Notes: SCCS Variable 1649 (Frequency of Internal Warfare, Resolved Rating) indicates that "internal warfare seems to be absent or rare". Further, SCCS Variable 1654 (Pacification), indicates that the society is "not pacified for all or part of the twenty-five-year time period". (Source of information: Ember and Ember, 1992; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– Yes

Notes: SCCS Variable 1650 (Frequency of External Warfare, Resolved Rating) indicates that "external warfare seems to occur every year, but usually only during a particular season" (Ember and Ember, 1992; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– No

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicating that the Lengua would recruit new members.

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

Notes: The Lengua have no political authority beyond the local community, which is reflective of autonomous bands and villages (*Ethnographic Atlas* column 33, Murdock, 1967; retrieved from Divale, 2004). Although chiefs are present, "There are really no social distinctions, the Chiefs only holding rule when it is for the common good, such as in time of war" (Grubb, 1913:188). Religious practitioners are

also present, and are responsible for protecting villagers from supernatural evil, foretelling future events, and arranging the weather (Grubb, 1913:146-147). Religion does not exist within a distinct sphere but rather permeates all aspects of life. Because the religious group is coterminous with Lengua society, the religious group is considered to have political support.

↳ Is religious infrastructure paid for by the polity:

– No

Notes: Religious infrastructure is not present among the Lengua.

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– No

Notes: The religious group is considered to be coterminous with Lengua society; there is no conception of apostasy.

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– I don't know

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Each Lengua village has a religious practitioner (referred to in Grubb, 1913, as "witch-doctors") whose main task is to protect the village from supernatural evils (Grubb, 1913:145). The practitioner additionally has the capabilities of arranging the weather and foretelling future events (Grubb, 1913:146-147).

↳ Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for a hierarchy among Lengua religious practitioners.

↳ Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:

– Yes

Notes: Each Lengua village has a religious practitioner (referred to in Grubb, 1913, as "witch-doctors") whose main task is to protect the village from supernatural evils (Grubb, 1913:145). The practitioner additionally has the capabilities of arranging the weather and foretelling future events (Grubb, 1913:146-147).

↳ Are religious leaders chosen:

– I don't know

↳ Are leaders considered fallible:

– I don't know

↳ Are close followers or disciples of a religious leader required to obediently and unquestionably accept the leader's pronouncements on all matters:

– I don't know

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also "oral scriptures" (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– No

Notes: The Lengua "...have no written records, and no system of carefully transmitted tradition..." (Grubb, 1913:115).

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– No

Notes: According to Murdock and Wilson (1972), Column 6, Large or Impressive Structures [Note: Equivalent to SCCS Variable 66], "There are no structures in the community that are appreciably larger or more impressive than the usual residential dwellings".

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Notes: The Lengua "...have left no permanent remains behind them, no cities, temples, or even burial mounds" (Grubb, 1913:111).

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of pilgrimages.

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body.

Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: The Lengua believe in "immortality of the soul" (Grubb, 1913:115).

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– Yes

Notes: "[The Lengua's] idea is that during sleep his soul detaches itself from his body, passing out through the chest, and actually does the things that he dreams about" (Grubb, 1913:127).

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: "Speaking generally, three ideas seem to prevail regarding the future abode of the soul...[1] the aphanagak [soul] continues to wander disconsolately about the country in company with its kindred spirits...[2] it moves over to the west, to the cities of the dead...[3] the dead inhabit a world beneath the earth" (Grubb, 1913:125).

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "above" space:

– No

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "below" space:

– Yes

Notes: "Speaking generally, three ideas seem to prevail regarding the future abode of the soul...[1] the aphanagak [soul] continues to wander disconsolately about the country in company with its kindred spirits...[2] it moves over to the west, to the cities of the dead...[3] the dead inhabit a world beneath the earth" (Grubb, 1913:125).

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined horizontal space:

– Yes

Notes: "Speaking generally, three ideas seem to prevail regarding the future abode of the soul...[1] the aphanagak [soul] continues to wander disconsolately about the country in company with its kindred spirits...[2] it moves over to the west, to the cities of the dead...[3] the dead inhabit a world beneath the earth" (Grubb, 1913:125).

Reincarnation in this world:

– I don't know

Notes: "While the kilyikhama [evil spirits] appear to be continually endeavoring in some form or other, such as that of an insect or some small animal, to obtain possession of a body, the aphanagak [spirits of

the departed], on the contrary, have never been supposed to attempt to enter the bodies of the living, with the exception that an indistinct idea seems to prevail that they sometimes seek reincarnation as a new-born child. This theory, however, is by no means analogous to that of the transmigration of the soul, of which the Indian knows nothing, but presupposes an occasional attempt, sometimes successful, to oust the spirit that would naturally belong to the child at birth" (Grubb, 1913:121).

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

Notes: "A grave is hastily dug [as to bury the body before sunset] with wooden diggers, and the body, loosened from the pole [used to transport it], is forced into a sitting posture inside" (Grubb, 1913:160).

↳ Cremation:

– Yes

Notes: "A murderer--that is, according to the Indian idea, a man who kills one of his own tribe-- is not only executed for the crime, but his body is burnt, and the ashes scattered to the four winds. The Indian believes that after such treatment his spirit cannot take human form, and remains in the after-world shapeless and unrecognizable, and therefore unable to mingle with its kindred spirits, or to enjoy such social intercourse as exists" (Grubb, 1913:120).

↳ Mummification:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of mummification.

↳ Interment:

– Yes

Notes: "A grave is hastily dug [as to bury the body before sunset] with wooden diggers, and the body, loosened from the pole [used to transport it], is forced into a sitting posture inside" (Grubb, 1913:160).

↳ Corpse is flexed (legs are bent or body is crouched):

– Yes

Notes: (Grubb, 1913:160).

↳ Corpse is extended (lying flat on front or back):

– No

↳ Corpse is upright (where body is interred in standing position):

– No

↳ Cannibalism:

– No

Notes: "Cannibalism is not practised" (Hawtrey, 1901:288).

↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying):

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of exposing bodies to the elements.

↳ Feeding to animals:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of feeding corpses to animals.

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of co-sacrifices in burials.

Are grave goods present:

– No

Notes: "The personal belongings and animals of the deceased are destroyed at his death, evidently with the idea that they may prove useful to him in the after-life. The reason given by the Indian for doing this is that the ghost would otherwise haunt the relatives" (Grubb, 1913:122-123).

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

Notes: "The rites to be performed alter according to the circumstances of death, but there is never any variation in the purification ceremony, the words at the graveside, the plants laid thereon, and the position of the body in the grave. The burning of the village and the destruction of the property of the deceased are always customary" (Grubb, 1913:163). "These rites having been performed, the body is placed in the grave in a sitting posture, with the face towards the west..." (ibid, pg. 163).

↳ In cemetery:

– No

Notes: No mention of cemeteries in ethnographic evidence.

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of family crypts.

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– I don't know

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Notes: See questions below for more information regarding Lengua supernatural beings.

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: "Their whole mythology is founded upon their idea of the Creation, of which we know only the bare outlines. The Creator of all things, spiritual and material, is symbolized by a beetle" (Grubb, 1913:114).

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

Notes: No monarch is present among the Lengua.

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

Notes: No monarch is present among the Lengua.

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– I don't know

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– No

Notes: "...there was an original First cause, a Creator who planned and made everything, but that He now takes no part in the governance of the universe, and, therefore, neither rewards nor punishes" (Grubb, 1913:116).

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– I don't know

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:

– I don't know

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:

– Yes

Notes: "Holding as he [the Lengua] does that the Creator takes no interest in the affairs of man, he naturally renders him no worship; in fact, he worships nothing, and his efforts are confined to avoiding the consequences of evil-doing on earth and to warding off the malignant kilyikhama, who, he holds, are continually seeking to mar his happiness" (Grubb, 1913:117).

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:

– No

Notes: "...there was an original First cause, a Creator who planned and made everything, but that He now takes no part in the governance of the universe, and, therefore, neither rewards nor punishes" (Grubb, 1913:116). Because the high god does not partake in the governance of the universe, and there are no ethnographic examples of the high god communicating with the living, it is assumed that the high god does not communicate with the living.

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Yes

Notes: "...the aphanagak or departed souls of men in the shade world (pischischi, shadows), merely continue their present life, only of course in a disembodied state" (Grubb, 1913:120). "The soul on leaving the body is supposed to be astonished, and no to realize quite what has happened. It hovers about the village and neighborhood for a time, generally estimated at one month, after which period the mourning feast takes place. The natives then suppose themselves to be no longer haunted by the deceased's spirit, which they imagine to have left the neighborhood for good and to have passed to the realms of the dead" (Grubb, 1913:122).

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world:

– I don't know

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– No

Notes: "The spirits of the dead appear to take no interest in the living, nor, beyond causing uncanny feeling when supposed to be hovering about, do they seem in the least to influence those left behind. Their very names are not mentioned, and every effort is made by the living to forget them" (Grubb, 1913:120-121).

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– I don't know

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:

– No

Notes: "The spirits of the dead appear to take no interest in the living, not, beyond causing uncanny feelings when supposed to be hovering about, do they seem in the least to influence those left behind. Their very names are not mentioned, and every effort is made by the living to forget them" (Grubb, 1913:120-121).

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

Notes: The Lengua "...retain a belief in an original Creator, in the immortality of the soul, and in the existence of these powerful and numerous evil personifications, which they call kilyikhama" (Grubb, 1913:115). "That these kilyikhama are not the deified soul of men seems clear from the fact that there is no veneration shown them, but whether the Indian idea was originally that they were a distinct spiritual creation, or simply the souls of a prehistoric race, is not clear" (Grubb, 1913:119).

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– Yes

Notes: "Although all [Lengua] believe firmly in the existence of these [kilyikhama] spirits, and although they hold that they can be seen by man, yet I have never met an Indian who, on being closely questioned has seriously professed to have seen one" (Grubb, 1913:119).

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– Yes

Notes: "But it is quite common to hear them assert that they have heard [kilyikhama], and felt that they were near" (Grubb, 1913:119).

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– I don't know

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: "The old man told me that, when it thunders, it is an indication that the thunder-bird is angry, and is seeking to punish them by fire from the sky, for ever since the bird lost its fire it has had to eat its food raw" (Grubb, 1913:99).

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: Lengua supernatural beings included a vague and otiose creator deity (symbolized by a beetle), kilyikhama (malignant spirits), aphantak (departed souls of men, who would stay around for about a month after death, then traveling to the afterlife), and departed souls of

lower creations. These beings do not appear to be organized into any type of pantheon.

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:

– No

↳ Organized hierarchically:

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of supernatural monitoring.

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of messianic beliefs.

Is an eschatology present:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of an eschatology.

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of required celibacy.

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of required castration.

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Yes

Notes: "The training necessary to qualify an Indian to become a witch-doctor consists, in the first place, in severe fastings, and especially in abstention from fluid" (Grubb, 1913:146).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of food taboos.

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of required permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of human sacrifice.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of human sacrifice.

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of human sacrifice.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale "ceremonies" and "festivals."

– I don't know

Notes: The Lengua hold feasts for special occasions and religious purposes. "Although feasts are connected in great measure with their religion, such as it is, they also partake very largely of the social

element" (Grubb, 1913:177). However, it is unclear if participation is mandatory.

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A band

Notes: The Lengua have no political authority beyond the local community, which is reflective of autonomous bands and villages (Ethnographic Atlas column 33, Murdock, 1967; retrieved from Divale, 2004). Additionally, the Lengua have neither patrilineal nor matrilineal kin groups or exogamy. Source of information: Ethnographic Atlas (Murdock, 1967), Columns 19, 20, 22. "There are really no social distinctions, the Chiefs only holding rule when it is for the common good, such as in time of war" (Grubb, 1913:188).

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of formal education.

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence of a formal bureaucracy within the Lengua society. The Lengua have no political authority beyond the local community, which is reflective of autonomous bands and villages (Ethnographic Atlas column 33, Murdock, 1967; retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Notes: SCCS Variable 20 (Food Storage) indicates that no food storage is present (Murdock and Morrow, 1970; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Notes: SCCS Variable 14 (routes of land transport) indicates that unimproved trails are used (Murdock and Morrow, 1970; Retrieved from Divale, 2004). Presumably, transportation infrastructure is absent.

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Notes: According to Tuden and Marshall (1972), Column 10, Police [Note: Equivalent to SCCS Variable 90], "police functions are not specialized or institutionalized at any level of political integration, the maintenance of law and order being left exclusively to informal mechanisms of social control, to private retaliation, or to sorcery".

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Notes: According to Tuden and Marshall (1972), Column 9, Judiciary [Note: Equivalent to SCCS Variable 89], "Supreme judicial authority is lacking at any level above that of the local community".

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Notes: Because the Lengua do not have institutionalized judges or police, it can be assumed that a formal legal code is not present. Additionally, there is no ethnographic evidence for the presence of a formal legal code.

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Notes: The Lengua are "...a people who have no written language..." (Grubb, 1913:111).

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Notes: The Lengua rely primarily on hunting, with fishing and gathering as secondary sources of subsistence. Casual agriculture supplements the diet. Source of information from Ethnographic Atlas (Murdock, 1962-1971), retrieved from Divale, 2004; Variables 203-207, 232.

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Gathering
- Hunting (including marine animals)
- Fishing
- Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards

Notes: The Lengua rely primarily on hunting, with fishing and gathering as secondary sources

of subsistence. Casual agriculture supplements the diet. Source of information from Ethnographic Atlas (Murdock, 1962-1971), retrieved from Divale, 2004; Variables 203-207, 232.